

Development of media competence of students in practical undergraduate conditions

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ANNOTATION

This article describes the development of practical knowledge of students in the educational process, the effectiveness of practical training and the qualities of training students for practical training.

Keywords: higher education, practical training in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

INTRODUCTION

Determining the priorities for the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities, who think independently, to a new level in terms of quality, modernization of higher education , in order to develop the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies:

1. The following:

a) The concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 (hereinafter referred to as the Concept) should be approved in accordance with Appendix 1 and should include the following: development of public-private partnerships in the field of higher education, state and non-state

higher education in the regions to increase the level of higher education coverage from 50 percent based on the organization of the activities of educational institutions, to create a healthy competitive environment in the field, to make the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University the flagship of higher education institutions of our country; at least 10 higher education institutions in the republic are included in the list of higher education institutions in the first 1,000 places of the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Nearer Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities), including the inclusion of the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University in the list of the first 500 higher education institutions; step-by-step transfer of the educational process to the credit-module system in higher education institutions; based on international experiences, introduction of advanced standards of higher education, including gradual transition from education focused on acquiring theoretical knowledge to an educational system focused on the formation of practical skills in educational programs; to raise the content of higher education to a new level in terms of quality, to establish a system of highly qualified personnel training that will contribute to the sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors and find their place in the labor market; ensuring academic independence of higher education institutions; attracting foreign investments, expanding the scope of paid services, and establishing technoparks, foresights, technology transfer, start-up, accelerator centers in higher education institutions at the expense of other extra-budgetary funds, as well as the socio-economic development of their respective sectors, industries and regions bringing to the level of research and forecasting scientific-practical institutions; The publication of articles by professors and teachers of higher education institutions, researchers, doctoral students, undergraduate and graduate students in prestigious international scientific journals with a high impact factor,

increasing the citation rate of articles, as well as the promotion of republican scientific journals to international scientific and technical standards. ensure that the database is gradually entered.

Turning Uzbekistan's higher education system into a "hub" implementing international education programs in Central Asia;

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Practical training classes can be divided into two types. These are practical classes in subjects with and without lectures (for example, foreign languages). Practical training classes are conducted in strict accordance with science programs and work programs, as well as calendar thematic plans. A list of necessary literature for practical training will be provided. In the practical classes where there is a lecture class, the materials learned in the lecture classes are mainly reinforced with the help of exercises.

Practical training is used to achieve the following goals:

- arrangement of theoretical material.
- formation of skills.
- control of knowledge.

The effectiveness of practical training is determined by the quality of training students for practical training. The preparation of those who come out with lectures and news, and those who receive education, will be important. Technological maps are developed for each exercise.

CONCLUSION

It is important to correctly define the educational goals of each subject.

The content of the general educational goals is determined based on the guiding goals. The teacher will develop the technology of conducting practical training, the development of the lesson and the technological map. The development of lesson plans and technological maps for each lesson allows for a complete design and effective organization of the educational process. The successful movement of each of the elements indicated in the system of their activity by the student in the performance of independent work determines the following management actions of the teacher: planning, organization and monitoring and evaluation. For self-checking, the task (test, question, task and exercise) recommended for each training session provides continuous self-evaluation of the current pedagogical control and the level of achievement of the educational goals observed by the student.

REFERENCES

Karlibaev P Matmuratova G. **The development of students' capacities for self-evaluation as a pedagogical issue.** 2022/12 Журнал Science and Education in Karakalpakstan. Том 1 №4/1 стр 245-248